

Strengthening Upstream Circular Economy Governance in Kenya: Policy Recommendations from a Multi-Stakeholder Assessment

Beth Mbesu

State Department for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (SDTVET), Kenya

ORCID: 0009-0002-7420-3196

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Abstract

Kenya has made significant progress in downstream circular economy (CE) interventions, including waste management policies and recycling programs. However, upstream circular economy (UCE)—designing out waste before it is created—remains nascent. This paper presents findings from the UCERA (Upstream Circular Economy Readiness Assessment) validation workshop held in Nairobi on 1st April 2026, organized by UNIDO, the Ministry of Industry of Kenya, and Demos Helsinki. Drawing on participatory assessment involving six Kenyan government entities (SDTVET, MECCF, SDEP, NEMA, KNCPC, and MITI), the paper identifies key gaps in coordination, policy focus, and skills development. It offers recommendations for strengthening upstream CE governance, including digitizing assessment tools, introducing anonymous feedback mechanisms, leveraging Kenya's mobile money infrastructure (M-PESA), integrating upstream principles into TVET curricula, and planning for a just transition for informal sector workers (e.g., Dandora waste pickers, mitumba traders). The paper concludes that Kenya is ready for upstream CE, provided that enforcement, capacity building, and institutional coordination are prioritized. The findings are relevant to policymakers, development partners, TVET institutions, and researchers working on circular economy transitions in emerging economies.

Keywords: Upstream circular economy, Kenya, UCERA, policy governance, TVET, just transition, informal sector, M-PESA.

1. Introduction

Kenya has emerged as a leader in downstream circular economy (CE) interventions in Africa, with policies such as the Sustainable Waste Management Act (2022) and Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) regulations driving progress in waste collection, recycling, and plastic reduction. However, downstream CE captures only a fraction of material value and often relies on informal, unregulated labor. The more transformative opportunity lies in upstream circular economy (UCE): designing out waste before it is created through eco-design, material passports, component harvesting, and remanufacturing.

Recognizing this gap, the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), in collaboration with the Ministry of Industry of Kenya and Demos Helsinki, convened a focused session on 1st April 2026 in Nairobi. The session aimed to validate the "Upstream by Design" policy guide and to assess Kenya's readiness for UCE adoption using the Upstream Circular Economy Readiness Assessment (UCERA) framework.

This paper presents the author's personal feedback and strategic observations from that session. It identifies key gaps in Kenya's current policy landscape, offers recommendations for strengthening UCE governance, and argues that Kenya is ready to embrace upstream circularity—provided that enforcement, capacity building, and just transition planning are prioritized. The paper is intended for policymakers, development partners, TVET institutions, and researchers working on circular economy transitions in emerging economies.

2. Methodology

The findings in this paper are based on the author's direct participation in the UCERA validation workshop held at the Pullman Hotel in Nairobi on 1st April 2026. The workshop was organized by UNIDO, the Ministry of Investments, Trade and Industry (MITI) of Kenya, and Demos Helsinki.

The six government entities that participated were:

- State Department for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (SDTVET)
- Ministry of Environment, Climate Change and Forestry (MECCF)
- State Department for Economic Planning (SDEP) – operating within the National Treasury and Economic Planning
- National Environment Management Authority (NEMA)

- Kenya National Cleaner Production Centre (KNCPC)
- Ministry of Investments, Trade and Industry (MITI)

Representatives from these entities worked in sector-specific groups to assess readiness across three UCERA domains: governmental structures, policy procedures and methods, and skills, data, and knowledge.

This paper synthesizes the author's observations, group discussions, and plenary feedback. It does not represent the official position of any participating organization. Rather, it is offered as a personal contribution to the public conversation on upstream circular economy governance in Kenya and beyond.

3. Overall Impression: Toolkit Fit for Purpose

The Upstream by Design policy guide and the associated readiness assessment toolkit were well received. In my view, the toolkit is fit for its intended purpose, because it does not merely assess readiness in theory but actively creates the conditions for the very collaboration and awareness it seeks to measure. Specifically, it:

- i. Enabled honest self-reflection and cross-ministry dialogue
- ii. Demonstrated its practical value as an instrument for advancing upstream circular economy (UCE) governance.

4. Most Valuable Outcome: Breaking Silos Through Honest Self-Assessment

One of the most valuable outcomes was how the validation process created a rare forum where different ministries could openly discuss how their actions, or inactions, support or hinder UCE efforts in other ministries, and the country at large. The self-assessment helped us confront uncomfortable truths and see the bigger picture of a whole-of-government approach i.e.:

- i. Helped us sit with the uncomfortable truths of our own failings and shortcomings
- ii. Raised awareness of current gaps, their effects and showed what needs to be done to fill them
- iii. Even unspoken truths were still registered by each individual in their bare, stark honesty, the essence of self-evaluation
- iv. Opened up discussion on what is happening in other ministries, helping us see the bigger picture of a whole-of-government approach

Hence it was key to breaking down traditional siloed approaches and building a foundation for inter-ministerial collaboration and synergy.

5. Critical Points for Toolkit 2.0 and Beyond

5.1 Wider Reach, Anonymity, and Un-editable Feedback

The assessment exercise was designed as a learning process and a test of the toolkit's usability. The information generated was not intended for any operational or evaluative use beyond assessing whether the tool achieves its intended objective of enabling honest self-reflection and cross-ministry dialogue. However, the exercise was necessarily limited to the representatives physically present in the room. To strengthen the toolkit for wider application, we can consider:

- i. *Digitizing the tool* – Will enable easy sharing of the assessment to a much wider audience across and beyond departments, allowing many more officials to participate.
- ii. *Introduce anonymous submission of feedback* – Will allow officials to share institutional failings, bureaucratic bottlenecks, and enforcement gaps without fear of reprisal, capturing what might otherwise remain unsaid. It is the uncomfortable truths that must be exposed and highlighted for action.
- iii. *Ensure feedback cannot be edited once submitted and is collated into a whole* – The output should be automatically aggregated and made sharable across all participating ministries without any possibility of editing or whitewashing uncomfortable truths. This will enable everyone involved in policy development to receive uniform, unaltered feedback, direct from responders to the entire forum of participants and policy developers, so that the data remains true and actionable.

5.2 Kenya's Context: Vibrant Downstream CE, Emerging Upstream CE

Kenya's circular economy policy is currently guided by the Sustainable Waste Management Act of 2022 and Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) regulations. Key efforts to date have focused on plastics reduction, waste segregation, and green manufacturing. While these have created jobs and reduced environmental impact, most of our success has been in downstream CE (DCE). Upstream CE (UCE) is still nascent. The key fact to be considered include:

- i. DCE (waste recycling, often informal) supports hundreds of thousands of households and have been embraced by these actors. This is evident by dumpsites like Dandora have informal cartels controlling who gets access to the dumpsite and the rules of engagement.

This highlighting both the scale and complexity of DCE, and a call for a just transition to UCE.

- ii. The greening of the TVET curriculum remains largely downstream-focused. There is a current curriculum being developed on Waste management. This calls for a need to shift and embed UCE as well into TVET curricula to reach the next generation of manufacturers and technicians early.

5.3 Leveraging Existing Downstream Infrastructure for Upstream Goals

The same networks that support DCE can be leveraged for upstream interventions. This would accelerate EPR and create formal livelihood pathways for informal waste workers. Waste aggregators, transporters, and informal recyclers can support UCE. E.g. Returning packaging materials (e.g., bottles) to manufacturers could use the same aggregators to clean and pack them, and the same transporters to move them back to factories of origin. This would not only accelerate EPR but also create formal livelihood pathways for those currently in informal waste management work.

5.4 Mobile Money & Digital Incentives

Kenya's well-penetrated mobile money infrastructure (e.g., M-PESA) offers a unique opportunity to incentivize upstream behavior in a just and transparent manner. For instance: Users could earn loyalty points ("bonga points") for returning packaging to manufacturers, ensuring justice, fairness, and transparency while accelerating EPR adoption.

5.5 Youth, Social Media, and TVET as Change Agents

Kenya is a young country, and this demographic is highly active on social media, open to difficult conversations, and ready to act. SDTVET has wide penetration across the country, in its network of TVET institution. Additionally, SDTVET is already keenly reviewing TVET curricula to include circularity. However, these curricula still focus on downstream CE.

- i. *Demographics*: Kenya's Median age is approximately 20.5 years with over 70% of population under 30
- ii. *Awareness creation* on UCE can ride on social media and be amplified through the SDTVET network. This demographic group defined in i. above are the main consumers of both social media, TVET education and SDTVET initiatives
- iii. *SDTVET's solid waste handler curriculum* (waste handlers were formally referred to as chokora, a derogatory term). This has dignified the profession and positioned these

technicians as key players in CE. However, the curricula remain downstream-focused. There is a need to review it before rollout to include the role of solid waste handlers in supporting UCE. For instance, instead of a recycling mentality, training can be geared to engage them in material recovery and returning materials to the producer without reducing material value (recycling often loses material value and expends energy; both avoidable if UCE is embedded)

- iv. *TVET's CBET approach* has key focus on community engagement initiatives, recognition of prior learning, and practical-oriented training. These reforms are currently ongoing, embedding Upstream Circular Economy is very timely. As such, TVET education is a platform to all reach the youth and position them as change agents.

5.6 Enforcement Over Voluntary Action

CE is an emerging field in Kenya; waste remains a daily pain for overwhelmed municipalities. Kenya is ready for UCE, but voluntary initiatives alone will not suffice. The need for capacity building on Upstream CE and stronger enforcement of policies and regulations governing UCE is evident.

There have been complete bans (e.g., single-use plastics), which were a good move but may eventually harm the economy if alternatives and just transitions are not planned for and embedded in the National CE policy.

5.7 Just Transition: The Mitumba Example

The case of mitumba (imported secondhand clothing) is instructive. A complete ban on importation of mitumba clothing has failed severally. This is because the sector supports a large portion of the informal textile sector and provides affordable clothing to the majority who would not afford new clothing. To minimize this resistance, a just transition is required. This would mean creating alternative livelihoods for mitumba sector actors. This can take the form of absorbing them into the supply chain of new textile, production of natural and more sustainable fibre, and even involving them as participants in UCE (e.g., textile refurbishment, redesign, or material recovery).

5.8 Africa's Advantage: Less Retrofitting Needed

Kenya, and Africa more broadly, has a distinct advantage: being among the least industrialized regions, there is less need for costly retrofitting of existing factories to adopt UCE principles. A new investor setting up a factory today can integrate UCE from day one far more easily than a

long-established manufacturer in a heavily industrialized country. This is a leverage point we should actively promote.

6. Conclusion: Kenya Is Ready for Upstream Circular Economy

In my judgement, Kenya is ready for Upstream Circular Economy. This readiness is not theoretical; it is already visible in our eagerness to embrace circular economy principles and in our proven ability to implement Downstream CE at scale, even under informal and resource-constrained conditions. The very fact that waste recycling networks now support hundreds of thousands of households, that mobile money has become ubiquitous, and that dumpsites like Dandora have become economic hubs (however imperfect) demonstrates a national appetite for circular solutions that goes beyond policy rhetoric. With proper awareness, targeted capacity building, and the right institutional support, Kenya is prepared to rethink its approach and develop a more robust circular economy policy that places upstream interventions at the center. Several additional indicators point to Kenya's readiness to uptake UCE:

- i. The government has already demonstrated political will through the Sustainable Waste Management Act of 2022 and EPR regulations, showing that legislative frameworks can be enacted when the political consensus exists.
- ii. Kenya has a relatively young and adaptable industrial base, meaning fewer legacy systems and less resistance from entrenched high-carbon or linear industries compared to older industrialized economies.
- iii. The country has a vibrant culture of entrepreneurship and innovation, particularly in the green economy, with startups already exploring waste-to-value models.
- iv. With CE being regional and global trends, Kenya's commitments under the African Circular Economy Alliance and growing donor interest creates both accountability and momentum.
- v. Kenya has already demonstrated the ability to mobilize collective action around environmental challenges, from the plastic bag ban to the recent movement against plastic pollution in national parks.

These are not small achievements; they are proof of concept for what is possible when policy, public awareness, and political will align.

That said, this will not be easy. As highlighted throughout this document, significant challenges remain: weak enforcement of existing regulations, fragmented institutional coordination, the political economy of informal cartels (such as those controlling Dandora dumpsite), the need for just transition planning for sectors like mitumba, and the risk of relying on voluntary initiatives rather than binding commitments. These obstacles are real, but they are not insurmountable.

The Upstream by Design toolkit itself offers a pathway; not by pretending these challenges do not exist, but by forcing us to name them, assess them honestly, and design policies that address them head-on.

I am eager to see Kenya take up this challenge. The opportunity before us is extraordinary: to build a manufacturing economy that designs out waste from the very first sketch, to dignify and formalize the work of thousands of waste handlers, and to demonstrate to other emerging economies that upstream circularity is not a luxury of the rich but a strategic choice for the ambitious. I do not underestimate the difficulty of the road ahead, but I am convinced that with sustained collaboration between ministries, with UNIDO and Demos Helsinki, and across the private sector and civil society, Kenya can become a model for upstream circular economy governance in Africa and beyond. I look forward to walking that road together.

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